

EVERYTHING

BRANDED

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Executive Summary

The proposed assessment has projected light on theoretical frameworks. Models such as the Four Stages and the Six Building Blocks of the CBBE Model and the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model have been applied and evaluated in the context of reputation, brand identity and image. Brand identity of Everything Branded UK encompasses images as well as words, the brand shares with its consumers. In the B2B context, these models have the capacity to encourage brands to set them apart from the crowd and streamline their brand identity. The culture of Everything Branded UK helps employees to work with higher motivation and greater efficiency. It has been identified that Everything Branded UK also uses a range of digital marketing strategies that assist the brand to consistently interact with the target audience. However, it has been observed that Everything Branded UK comprises limitations to specific aspects. Therefore, it can be stated that Everything Branded UK should have more growth strategies that will assist the brand to stay competent. It can be suggested that all these factors such as vision, mission and values of Everything Branded UK are supported by its logo, approaches, and other aspects. The brand has aligned its enthusiastic culture and nature with the brand elements to emphasis on the mission, vision and values.

1.0 Introduction

The current assessment aims to analyse the aspects that are related to brand identity, reputation and image. These factors are considered to be the most important aspects of paving the pathway of progress and success at the same time. The proposed study will shed light on theoretical frameworks. Models such as Four Stages and the Six Building Blocks of the CBBE Model and the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model will be described and evaluated in the context of brand identity, reputation and image. Along with this, the competitiveness, opportunities, and brand elements of the selected company, Everything Branded UK will be analysed in the rest part of the report.

2.0 Theoretical Framework

2.1 The Four Stages and the Six Building Blocks of the CBBE Model

Figure 1: Keller's CBBE Model

(Source: Qualtrics, 2023)

2.1.1 Brand Identity

Brand identity is one of the major components (refer to the provided diagram) of the CBBE model. Brand identity is considered to be the brand salience that helps customers to identify and differentiate a brand in an intense market competition (Chatzipanagiotou *et al.*, 2019). Brand

identity of Everything Branded UK encompasses words as well as images, the company shares with its customers. Brand identity is a critical component of the entire model and must be supported with the rest of the elements (Qualtrics, 2023).

2.1.2 Brand Meaning

Brand meaning stands for the way by which consumers want to know more and more of the brand. Questions that consist of factors such as style, durability, reliability, customer experience and the values of the Everything Branded UK refer to brand meaning to customers of the company. Two pillars of the aspect will be brand performance and brand imagery (Qualtrics, 2023).

2.1.3 Brand Response

When customers revert to their queries and what Everything Branded UK shares with them is typically categorised into two parts or sections such as feelings and judgements (Qualtrics, 2023). This aspect of the CBBE model is made up of factors such as consideration, quality and other similar components (refer to the provided diagram). Basically, customers assess how superior Everything Branded UK is for them.

Figure 2: Keller's CBBE Model

(Source: Mindtools, 2023)

2.1.4 Brand Relationship

In this stage of the CBBE model, Keller's state that when a customer is loyal and becomes aware of the brand and its meaning (refer to the provided diagram), the person will not purchase things from other platforms rather than Everything Branded UK (Mindtools, 2023). Everything Branded

UK needs to measure the progress with some beneficial KPIs such as Net Promoter Score or NPS in this stage.

2.2 The Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model

2.2.1 Head Station

This aspect or dimension of the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model helps to focus on the main or major operations of Everything Branded UK. Major operations of a brand includes reviewing the quality approaches of products or services, CRM, marketing and other relevant operations of the company (Basari and Shamsudin, 2020).

2.2.2 Strategy Station

Strategy station refers to the strategic direction and therefore the foundational areas of a brand. This aspect emphasises the actions and ideas that are generally adapted to foster greater transparency in strategic operations over the time. The five major parts of the strategy station are arenas, staging, differentiators, economic logics and process management. In strategy station, Everything Branded UK will highlight its strategies that are used by the company to reach its customers (Everything Branded, 2023).

2.2.3 Creativity Station

The creative station in the organisational context refers to the ability of an organisation to create imaginative and new ideas associated with projects, processes and other relevant factors. The major aim of approaching the creative station is to promote innovative approaches in a unique manner. Likewise, Everything Branded UK approaches various promotional products, helping business to grow more are some of the innovative approaches of the company (Everything Branded, 2023).

2.2.4 Communication Station

Communication is recognised to be the most important factor to stay relevant within the organisational context (Guffey and Loewy, 2019). Communication helps to share ideas and concepts with both the internal and external stakeholders of a company. The communication

station at Everything Branded UK refers to the communication channels the company uses to maintain the consistency in a unique manner (Everything Branded, 2023).

2.2.5 Human Power Station

The human power station of the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model typically focuses on the human resources of a company (Guffey and Loewy, 2019). The aspect defines or relates to the skilled workforce of a company to serve the customers.

2.2.6 The Critical Triplet Station

In line with the Triple Bottom Line theory, the critical triplet of a company can be the planet aspect, people aspect and profit aspect. A brand can prosper and grow based on these three aspects which will also help to focus on environmental and ethical concerns at the same time (Laosirihongthong *et al.*, 2020).

2.3 Comparing the CBBE model and the Six-Stations Corporate Identity model

2.3.1 Similarities in Principles

It has been observed that the CBBE model defines how an organisation can trigger its customers based on their brand value (Chatzipanagiotou *et al.*, 2019). Similar to that point, the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model helps to shed light on the major areas where a business has the opportunity to grow in a unique manner.

2.3.2 Differences in Principles

It has been observed that the CBBE model helps to focus or emphasis on the point of views of customers to perceive a brand (Chatzipanagiotou *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model helps to focus on the core areas where a business reflects its bases.

2.3.3 Potential Overlaps in Concepts

Both models have different areas or concepts to support organisational growth. Brand identification should be based on both the internal and external elements and how a brand responds to them.

Figure 3: B2B growth from digital channels in the UK

(Source: Statista, 2024)

2.3.4 Implications for Brand Analysis in Business-to-Business Context

As the Six-Stations Corporate Identity Model helps to identify areas where businesses can grow nowadays, digital channels are helping B2B businesses to grow in the UK (as demonstrated in the above figure) (Statista, 2024). In B2B contexts, these models have the capability to encourage companies to streamline their brand identity and set them apart from the crowd. This can contribute to the growth of a positive brand image in the B2B context.

3.0 Analysis of Everything Branded UK

3.1 Strategy factors

The major brand elements of Everything Branded UK: The major brand elements of Everything Branded UK are its logo, brand voice, brand name, colour, content, positioning, brand values and

so on. Basically, brand elements are the major factors of a company or brand that help customers to identify or differentiate the brand from its market competitors (Everything Branded, 2023).

How these elements align with mission, values and vision of Everything Branded UK: It has been observed that the brand operates with a defined aim and mission. The vision of the company is to create an impact in the worldwide promotional product industry. Mission statement of the company comprises doing something different for business and brands to help them and become the one-stop solution centre as well (Everything Branded, 2023). The values of the company include recruiting potential people to serve customers in the best possible manner. Everything Branded UK's some of the major organisational values are respect, listening, passion and more factors. Therefore, it can be stated that all these factors such as mission, vision and values of Everything Branded UK are covered by its approaches, logo and other aspects. The brands aligned its enthusiastic nature with the brand elements to highlight its mission, vision and values.

How these elements impact brand relationship in B2B context: These elements in the B2B context helps to make a greater impact day by day. Logo works as the brand identity whereas values are prioritised by customers to prefer Everything Branded UK rather than other brands in the same industry.

3.2 Communication factors

EB's communication across different digital channels: Across different digital platforms or channels Everything Branded UK uses and prioritises its own mediums to communicate with customers. Examples include platforms such as LinkedIn, Facebook, Google, Instagram, Twitter and more. With the help of an internet-enabled video connection, now connecting with employees and customers is the easiest task ever (GOROVEI, 2020).

How does EB use digital media to develop their brand identity: Everything Branded UK focuses on creating brand awareness through the improvement of its digital marketing strategy. It can be stated that Everything Branded UK uses digital media to reframe the brand identity in a unique manner (Everything Branded, 2023). The brand requires a unique voice as well as tone which resonates with the target audience of Everything Branded UK. In addition to this, the usage of digital media to improve brand identity also includes the creation of effective and lucrative content to influence customers. In fact, consistent communication is also a major element used by Everything Branded UK to develop its brand identity on digital media.

How are communication of EB's brand elements consistent across various digital platforms:

The communication of Everything Branded UK's brand elements across different digital platforms are consistent and supported with a range of factors that ultimately help the brand to perform in the most defined way (Hofacker *et al.*, 2020). It has been observed that Everything Branded UK prefers to share all the updates and news with its customers almost on a daily basis. The content of the brand also appears in a structured format which greatly resonates with the customers. And this is how the brand maintains consistency across different digital platforms.

3.3 Human Power factors

Figure 3: Everything Branded UK

(Source: Everything Branded, 2023)

Approach towards customer interactions regarding customer service, quality of products, services, and overall customer experience: Everything Branded UK is one of the leading companies in the promotional product industry of the UK and beyond. Therefore, it has been observed that being a leading brand the company never fails to attempt innovative approaches for its customers. Everything Branded UK engages its employees to work for the betterment of the customers as demonstrated in the above picture. Through helping customers with mutual agreements based on the desired outcomes help the company to share and communicate their

thoughts (Gabriel and Aguini, 2022). A skilled workforce helps them to interact with customers, share its quality approaches, streamline customer experience and other related factors (Everything Branded, 2023).

The significance of the company's staff in shaping customer experience: The skilled workforce of Everything Branded UK is one of the most competent workforce of the UK's promotional product industry. The workforce helps the company to share and interact with customers on a daily basis. The staff of Everything Branded UK interacts with customers by identifying their core needs, values and preferences to suggest the best products. This helps customers to focus on effective and quick solutions which make them feel valued. Communicating based on the core needs consistently is the major way the skilled workforce of the company focuses on shaping the customer experience (Keiningham *et al.*, 2020).

How does EB's engagement with customers affect its brand reputation and image: Creating engaging content and experiences is the core strategy of the brand to improve customers engagement (Everything Branded, 2023). When customers are engaged with the brand, they make a long-term journey with them which helps the company to generate a positive brand image and high organisational reputation. Similarly, EB's customer engagement with its customers greatly affects its brand reputation and image as well.

3.4 Reputation and Image Analysis

What does customer feedback imply for EB's brand reputation and image: Customer feedback and thoughts are the most important aspects to shape the organisational landscape. It has been observed that customers share their thoughts and perspectives when they feel attached with the brand itself. At Everything Branded UK they evaluate and analyse customers' feedback in order to gain insights into customers' perspective (Everything Branded, 2023). Basically, it can be stated that the brand evaluates customer feedback to create engaging experiences. This ultimately helps to shape the brand's reputation and image as customers begin to trust them. The analysis of customer feedback helps the brand to develop trust and credibility which results in a positive brand image and reputation as well.

How do the components of corporate identity interrelate to create brand image and reputation for EB: The components of corporate identity such as communication, strategic directions, HRM, brand values and other factors are closely related to the brand image and reputation in a unique

manner (Rosli and Nayan, 2020). These elements share and shape the reputation of the organisation by emphasising the quality of products and services and other approaches EB offers to its customers. This earns a strong reputation to EB in the competitive market.

3.5 Competitor Analysis

Identification of one key competitor of EB: As of current reports, it has been observed that one of the biggest competitors of EB in the UK's promotional products industry is Redbows Ltd (Approved Business, 2023). It has been identified that Redbows Ltd is also one of the leading distributors of promotional gift items, creative advertising gifts, marketing ideas for developing new business and so on.

How does their brand narration and imagery compare to EB: Compared to EB they have some more product options in their product category. It helps the brand to operate in the market more strategically (Approved Business, 2023). Also, it has been observed that EB shows market penetration and differentiation strategies to grow whereas Redbows Ltd mostly operates with product development strategy and more.

4.0 The Overall Brand Health

The overall health of a brand refers to its financial portfolio, product portfolio, performance, human resource development and other related factors that shape the growth of the company.

4.1 Opportunities

Figure 4: A robust CRM at Everything Branded UK

(Source: Everything Branded, 2023)

It has been observed that Everything Branded UK has a legitimacy and a strong history that make them more effective in the market. The operations of the brand have been shaped with multiple strategies and tactics that enable Everything Branded UK to achieve its goals and objectives in a quick manner. On the other hand, the brand has a wide range of product portfolios which aspire and inspire other businesses to connect with them. 12 years of experience and expertise in the promotional product industry allow the brand to be more productive day by day (Everything Branded, 2023). The organisational values of the brand help it to maintain transparency with customers while communicating (as demonstrated in the above picture). The brand has a strong culture that helps Everything Branded UK to embrace the authenticity of its products and services in a unique manner. The culture helps employees to work with motivation and higher efficiency. It has been observed that the brand also uses a range of digital marketing strategies that help the brand to consistently communicate with the target customers (Alghizzawi, 2019). The values of Everything Branded UK make it different from other similar brands with a similar product portfolio in the industry. On the other hand, it has been observed that Everything Branded UK encompasses a skilled workforce that enables the brand to operate in a strategic manner. The workforce is recognised as one of the best teams in the respective industry. The CRM of the company provides personalised services to its customers. The account managers of Everything Branded UK listen to the customers properly to make informed decisions. The product management team of Everything Branded UK helps the CRM to get and collect all the data regarding the product and its features. This further helps the team to share and gather insights from customers.

4.2 Challenges or Limitations

Despite having a range of features, it has been identified that Everything Branded UK is limited to some specific factors. The brand belongs to an industry which is least known to customers. This makes them less attractive in front of their customers. Thus, it can be stated that improving its portfolio is one of the major tasks the brand needs to accomplish as soon as possible. The brand also has a limited product portfolio compared to its competitors in the market. On the other hand, it has been identified that Everything Branded UK relies on the UK market heavily. This means that the brand will suffer as the UK economy suffers. The brand needs to focus on improving its global presence and other relevant aspects. In addition to this, Everything Branded UK's marketing

strategies are also limited compared to other brands. Therefore, the brand needs to create more effective strategies. The online presence of the company should be supported and streamlined due to an intense market competition. The competitive market and competitors like Redbows Ltd. can make it difficult for Everything Branded UK to operate across the UK.

5.0 Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be stated that having a great focus on improving the organisational reputation and brand image is impactful for accelerating growth in a unique manner. The proposed study helped to gather insights on the organisational factors and elements that shape the arena of brand reputation. Everything Branded UK is one of the leading brands that has a wide range of product portfolio. However, it has been identified that Everything Branded UK is limited to some particular factors. Therefore, it can be suggested to the brand that having more growth strategies will help the brand to remain competent.

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